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SEPARATION OF ORIGINAL ECG SIGNAL FROM THE NOISE MIXED SIGNAL DUE TO YAWN USING TEMPORAL PREDICTABILITY

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Abstract:

Signals recorded from the heart provide valuable information about the heart's electrical conduction system. This procedure of recording is called ECG, which used to assess patients with systemic disease, as well as monitoring during anesthesia and critically ill patients. But the signals are always contaminated by a drift and interference caused by several bioelectric phenomena, or by various types of noise, such as intrinsic noise from the recorder and noise from electrode-skin contact and distortion caused by power line interference, external electromagnetic fields. The noise or artifacts can even confuse a diagnosis due to a wrong interpretation. In this paper we utilize temporal predictability for noise cancellation with preserving the low frequency components and tiny features of the ECG.

Keywords: *ECG, Bio Signals, Noise, Temporal Predictability*

Introduction

The biomedical signal processing field has advanced to the stage of practical application of signal processing and pattern analysis techniques for efficient and improved non-invasive diagnosis, online monitoring of critical patients and rehabilitation.

The Electrocardiogram signal is one of the diagnosing approaches to detect heart disease. ECG signals provide significance information about heart functional conditions and circulation system. By placing the electrodes on body surface the electrical activity of the heart muscles can be measured. A typical ECG cycle waveform. The ECG signal is very weak ranging from 10 μ v

to $5\mu\text{v}$ with a frequency from 0.05 hz to 100hz. In addition the ECG signal is often corrupted with noise. Obtaining an ECG signal could be an easy task, but obtaining a reliable ECG signal to provide a clinic analysis by a specialist is a more complicated task

The predominant artifacts present in the ECG includes: power line interferences, electrode contact noise, motion artifacts . muscle contraction caused due to breathing(yawning), base line drift , instrumentation noise generated by electronic devices. The low frequency ST segments of ECG signals are strongly affected by these contamination, which lead to false diagram. The extraction of high-resolution ECG signals from recordings contaminated with back ground noise is an important issue to investigate. The goal for ECG signal enhancement is to separate the valid signal components from the undesired artifacts, so as to present an ECG that facilitates.

In this research power line interference and noise due to breathing mixed with ECG signal are separated out by using temporal predictability. A measure of temporal predictability is defined and used to separate linear mixture of signal. The temporal predictability of any signal mixture is less than that of any of its component source signal . This property can be used to recover source signal from a set of linear mixtures of those signals by finding an un-mixing matrix that maximizes a measure of temporal predictability for each recovered signal.

Problem Definition

I. TEMPORAL PREDICTABILITY

Consider a set of K statistically independent source signals $s = \{s_1 | s_2 | \dots | s_k\}^t$ where , where the i^{th} row in a is a signal s_i measured at n time points (the superscript t denotes the transpose operator). It is assumed throughout this article that source signals are statistically independent, unless stated otherwise. A set of $M \geq K$ linear mixtures $x = \{x_1 | x_2 | \dots | x_m\}^t$ of signals in s can be formed with an $M \times K$ mixing matrix $A : x = As$. If the rows of A are linearly independent, then any source signal s_i can be recovered from x with a $1 \times M$ matrix $W_i : S_i = W_i x$. The problem to be addressed here consists in finding an unmixing matrix $W = \{W_1 | W_2 | \dots | W_k\}^t$ such that each row vector W_i

recovers a different signal Y_i , where Y_i is a scaled version of a source signal S_i , for $K = M$ signals.

II. A SOLUTION STRATEGY

The method for recovering source signals is based on the following conjecture: the temporal predictability of a signal mixture X_i is usually less than that of any of the source signals that contribute to X_i . For example, the waveform obtained by adding two sine waves with different frequencies is more complex than either of the original sine waves.

This observation is used to define a measure $F(W_i, x)$ of temporal predictability, which is then used to estimate the relative predictability of a signal y_i recovered by a given matrix W_i , where $Y_i = W_i X$. If source signals are more predictable than any linear mixture Y_i of those signals, then the value of W_i , which maximizes the predictability of an extracted signal Y_i , should yield a source signal (i.e., $Y_i = C S_i$, where C is a constant).

An information-theoretic analysis of the function F proves that maximizing the temporal predictability of a signal amounts to differentially maximizing the power of Fourier components with the lowest (nonzero) frequencies. The function F is invariant with respect to the power of low-frequency components in signal mixtures and therefore tends to amplify differentially even very low power components, which have the lowest (nonzero) temporal frequency.

III. MEASURING SIGNAL PREDICTABILITY

The definition of signal predictability F used here is

$$F(W_i, x) = \log \frac{V(W_i, x)}{U(W_i, x)} = \log \frac{V_i}{U_i} = \log \frac{\sum_{\tau=1}^n (\bar{y}_{\tau} - y_{\tau})^2}{\sum_{\tau=1}^n (\tilde{y}_{\tau} - y_{\tau})^2}, \quad (1)$$

where $Y_{\tau} = W_i X_{\tau}$ is the value of the signal Y at time τ , and X_{τ} is a vector of K signal mixture values at time τ . The term U_i reflects the extent to which Y_{τ} is predicted by a short-term moving average \bar{y}_{τ} of values in y .

In contrast, the term V_i is a measure of the overall variability in y , as measured by the

extent to which Y_r is predicted by a long-term moving average Y_τ of values in y_τ . The predicted values Y_τ and \tilde{Y}_τ of Y_r are both exponentially weighted sums of signal values measured up to time $(\tau - 1)$, such that recent values have a larger weighting than those in the distant past:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}_\tau &= \lambda_S \tilde{y}_{(\tau-1)} + (1 - \lambda_S) y_{(\tau-1)} : 0 \leq \lambda_S \leq 1 \\ \bar{y}_\tau &= \lambda_L \bar{y}_{(\tau-1)} + (1 - \lambda_L) y_{(\tau-1)} : 0 \leq \lambda_L \leq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The half-life h_L of λ_L is much longer (typically 100 times longer) than the corresponding half-life h_S of λ_S . The relation between a half-life h and the parameter λ is defined as $\lambda = 2^{-1/h}$. Note that maximizing only V_i would result in a high variance signal with no constraints on its temporal structure. In contrast, minimizing only U would result in a DC signal. In both cases, trivial solutions would be obtained for W_i because V_i can be maximized by setting the norm of W_i to be large, and U can be minimized by setting $W_i = 0$. In contrast, the ratio V_i / U_i can be maximized only if two constraints are both satisfied : (1) y has a nonzero range (i.e.. high variance) and (2) the values in y change slowly over time. Note also that the value of F is independent of the norm of W_i , so that only changes in the direction of W_i affect the value of F .

IV. REDEFINING SIGNAL PREDICATABILITY

One counterexample to the temporal predictability conjecture is as follows. Consider two sine wave source signals $s_1 = s_1 + s_2$ is zero at all time points and is therefore quite predictable. While s is intuitively predictable, the operational definition of predictability F used here is robust with respect to such counterexamples. Specifically, the value of the function F is undefined for s because if $s = 0$ everywhere, then $V_i = U_i = 0$ and $F = \log 0/0$. Conversely, if the frequencies of s_1 and s_2 are not exactly the same then the value of F is no longer undefined.

The informal temporal predictability conjecture can now be restated formally in terms of the function F , as follows : if the value of F associated with a signal mixture x_i is not undefined, then the value of F of each mixture is greater than (or equal to) the value of F

of each source signal in that mixture.

V. EXTRACTING SIGNALS BY MAXIMIZING SIGNAL PREDICTABILITY

Extracting a Single Signal

Consider a scalar signal mixture y_i formed by the application of a $1 \times M$ matrix W_i to a set of $K = M$ signals x . Given that $y_i = W_i x$, equation (1.1) can be rewritten as

$$F = \log \frac{W_i \bar{C} W_i^t}{W_i \tilde{C} W_i^t}, \quad (3)$$

Where C is an $M \times M$ matrix of long-term covariances between signal mixtures and \tilde{C} is a corresponding matrix of short-term covariance. The long term covariance \bar{C} and the short-term covariance \tilde{C} between the i th and j th mixtures and defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C}_{ij} &= \sum_{\tau}^n (x_{i\tau} - \tilde{x}_{i\tau})(x_{j\tau} - \tilde{x}_{j\tau}) \\ \bar{C}_{ij} &= \sum_{\tau}^n (x_{i\tau} - \bar{x}_{i\tau})(x_{j\tau} - \bar{x}_{j\tau}). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Note that \tilde{C} and \bar{C} need to be computed only once for a given set of signal mixtures and that the terms $(x_{i\tau} - \bar{x}_{i\tau})$ and $(x_{i\tau} - \tilde{x}_{i\tau})$ can be precomputed using fast convolution operations.

Gradient ascent of F with respect to W_i could be used to maximize F , thereby maximizing the predictability of y_i , The derivative of F with respect to W_i , is

$$\nabla_{W_i} F = \frac{2W_i}{V_i} \bar{C} - \frac{2W_i}{U_i} \tilde{C}. \quad (5)$$

One optimization procedure (not used here) would consist of iteratively updating W_i until a maximum of F is located : $W_i = W_i + n \nabla_{W_i} F$, where n is a small constant (typically, $n = 0.001$).

Note that the function F is a ratio of quadratic forms. Therefore, F has exactly one global maximum and exactly one global minimum, with all other critical points being saddle points

(Borga, 1998). This implies that gradient ascent is guaranteed to find the global maximum in F. Unfortunately, repeated application of the above procedure to a single set of mixtures extracts the same (most predictable) source signal. While this can be prevented by using procedures such as Gram-Schmidt ortho normalization, a more elegant method for extracting all of the sources simultaneously exists, as described next.

Simultaneous Source Separation

The gradient of F is zero at a solution where, from equation (6)

$$W_i \bar{C} = \frac{V_i}{U_i} W_i \tilde{C}. \quad (6)$$

Extrema in F correspond to values of W_i , which has the form of a generalized eigen problem. Solutions for W_i can therefore be obtained as eigenvectors of the matrix $(C^{-1} \tilde{C})$, with corresponding eigen values $Y_i = V_i / U_i$. As noted above, the first such eigen vector defines a maxim in F, and each of the remaining eigenvectors defines saddle points in F.

Note that eigen problems have scaling characteristics of $O(N^3)$, where N is the number of signal mixtures. The matrix W can be obtained using a generalized eigenvalue routine. Results presented in this article were obtained using the Matlab eigen value function $W = \text{eig}(\bar{C}, \tilde{C})$. All k signals can then be recovered : $y = Wx$, where each row of y corresponds to exactly one extracted signal Y_i .

Separating Mixtures for $M > K$

If the number M of mixtures is greater than the number K of sources signals, then a standard procedure for reducing M consists of using principal component analysis (PCA). PCA is used to reduce the dimensionality of the signal mixtures by discarding eigenvectors of x that have eigenvalues close to zero. However, in this article, only mixtures for which $K = M$ are analyzed.

A Physical Interpretation

The solutions found by the method are the eigenvectors ($W_1, W_2 \dots W_m$) of the matrix

(\bar{C}, \tilde{C}) . These eigenvectors are orthogonal in the metric \bar{C} and \tilde{C}

$$\begin{aligned} W_i \tilde{C} W_j^t &= 0 \\ W_i \bar{C} W_j^t &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} W_i \tilde{C} W_j^t &= \sum_{\tau} (y_{i\tau} - \tilde{y}_{i\tau})(y_{j\tau} - \tilde{y}_{j\tau}) \\ W_i \bar{C} W_j^t &= \sum_{\tau} (y_{i\tau} - \bar{y}_{i\tau})(y_{j\tau} - \bar{y}_{j\tau}). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Given equations (7), a simple and physically realistic interpretation of the method can be demonstrated. Consider the short-term and long-term half-life parameters therefore $(y_{\tau} - \tilde{y}_{\tau}) \approx dy_{\tau} / d\tau = y'_{\tau}$. Second, if y has zero mean, then in the limit ($h_L \rightarrow \infty$). The long-term mean $\bar{y} \approx 0$, and therefore $(y_{\tau} - \bar{y}_{\tau}) \approx y_{\tau}$. In these limiting cases, equations (6) and (7) imply that h_s and h_L in the limits ($h_s \rightarrow 0$) and ($h_L \rightarrow \infty$). First, in the limit ($h_s \rightarrow 0$), the short-term mean is $\tilde{y} \approx y\tau^{-1}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} E[y'_i y'_j] &= 0 \\ E[y_i y_j] &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Where $E[\]$ denotes and expectation value. Thus, one interpretation of the method is that each signal $y_i = W_i x$ is uncorrelated with every other signal $y_j = W_j x$, and temporal derivative $y'_i = W_i x'$ of each extracted signal is uncorrelated with the temporal derivative $y'_j = W_j x'$ of every other extracted signal, where x' is a vector variable that is the temporal derivative of the mixtures x . Critically, if two signals, y_i and y_j are statistically independent then the conditions specified in equation (8) are met. Therefore, mixtures of independent signals are guaranteed to be separable by the method, at least in the limiting cases specified above.

Results and Simulations:

The method implementation is carried out on the mixture of ECG signal, Power Line Interference and Yawning (noise due to breathing) in MATLAB v7.12. In the above experiment, 3 source signals ECG Signal, Power Line noise and Noise due to breathing (Yawning) were used to generate 3 signal mixtures using a 3*3 mixing matrix, and these 3 mixtures were used as

input to the method. Each mixture signal was normalized to have zero-mean and unit variance. Each mixing matrix was obtained using the Matlab *randn* function. The short-term and long-term half-lives were set to $h_s=1$ and $h_l = 9000$, respectively. In this case, an un-mixing matrix was obtained as the solution to a generalised eigen value problem using the Matlab eigenvalue function $w = eig(\bar{C}, \bar{\epsilon})$.

Fig.1.: From Top to bottom ECG Signal ,Power Line noise and Noise due to breathing(Yawning).

Fig.2. Signal mixtures

Fig.3. From Top to Bottom Recovered ECG signal , Power Line noise and Noise due to breathing(Yawning).

Conclusion:

The noise present in ECG signal lead to improper diagnosis . The noise, whatever the source is, significantly contaminates the ECG signal and therefore makes its analysis difficult. The main objective of this paper was to implement Temporal Predictability for de-noising an ECG signal. We have successfully implemented it and recovered ECG signal from mixture of signals. The results indicate that this method can provide a reliable ECG signal for clinic analysis by a specialist.

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